

LAMB WAVE INSPECTION FOR THE REAL-TIME MONITORING OF COMPOSITE TAPE LAYING

E. J. Linstrom and S. C. Mantell
Department of Mechanical Engineering
University of Minnesota, Minneapolis, MN, USA

ABSTRACT

This paper presents preliminary research into the use of ultrasonic oblique insonification for the rapid inspection of composite parts during manufacture. This method will allow the monitoring of *in-situ* consolidation during processing. Since composite layers are added one at a time during this process, it is necessary to only determine the quality of the top most ply bond. Samples with poorly bonded top-most plies were constructed. Flatwise tensile testing was performed to determine the strength of this bond. The samples were also examined using an oblique insonification technique. Results indicate a difference between well bonded and poorly bonded top most plies can be detected.

INTRODUCTION

Cost effective and improved processing techniques for continuous fiber, polymer matrix composites must be developed before these materials will be widely used. Tape laying with *in-situ* consolidation and bonding is a thermoplastic part manufacturing process that yields short manufacturing times and places few limits on the size and shape of the part. In tape laying, heat and pressure are applied locally to bond the composite plies. To ensure that the process is working effectively, it is necessary to monitor its output. This paper discusses some preliminary work in using oblique insonification to monitor the tape laying process. For such a method to be successful it must meet the following criteria: it must be rapid enough to provide information in real-time; accurately find defects; and characterize defects so that their influence on the mechanical properties of the composite may be determined.

Review of the literature indicates that the inducement of Lamb (plate) waves induced in a composite plate by oblique insonification may meet the criteria. This research consists of three steps: the manufacture of poorly bonded parts; characterization of those parts by photomicrographs and mechanical testing; and characterization of those parts by Lamb wave inspection.

PREVIOUS RESEARCH

The use of Lamb wave methods to characterize composite materials has been the subject of much

interest in the literature. Impinging a sound wave unto a plate and observing the results is a standard nondestructive evaluation testing (NDT) technique. The theoretical under-pinning of the use of oblique insonification are discussed in Henneke[1]. A rigorous mathematical treatment is provided by Green and Milosavljevic[2]. Kline et al[3], Hosten and Deschamps[4], and Roklin and Wang[5] have used Lamb wave experiments to characterize composite material stiffness.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

CREATING POORLY BONDED SPECIMENS

Several 12 inch by 12 inch composite panels were manufactured with poorly bonded areas in the top-most ply. These panels are composed on ICI Fiberite 977-3 unidirectional pre-preg. A substrate of 15 plies was prepared in the autoclave using the manufacturer's specified pressure and temperature profiles. The top-most ply was applied using no pressure to create the poor bond. One Sample (Number 1) was manufactured correctly to provide a comparison to the others. Sample 5 was made of a 0°/90° lay-up, all the other samples are unidirectional. The difference in bonding can be seen in the photomicrographs of Figure 1. Previous research has focused on completely disbonded regions or foreign contaminants. This method of preparation is designed to produce parts that are bonded but whose bond strength is noticeably less than that of a well-made part.

MECHANICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF PARTS

To determine the actual bond strength of the top layer bond, the specimens were evaluated using a modified flatwise tensile test, based on ASTM C 297. This test was originally designed to test the strength of the adhesive in core/composite parts. The parts were pulled apart in the flatwise direction at a constant strain rate of 0.1 $\mu\text{m}/\text{sec}$. The failure stresses of the samples are plotted in Figure 2. We have yet to actually break apart a well-bonded sample and to do yet have a good number for comparison. It is interesting to note several differences in the testing between the well-bonded and the poorly bonded parts. The poorly bonded parts exhibited greater elongation than the well-bonded part. This is most likely due to the different nature of the poorly bonded epoxy matrix in failure and the behavior of the adhesive. Although the strain rates were kept constant the stress rates differed considerably. The stress-strain curves for the well-bonded samples which all failed at the adhesion line were almost vertical lines, while the stress-strain curves for the poorly bonded specimens were more gently sloping.

LAMB WAVE INSPECTION

A schematic diagram of the inspection set-up used is shown in Figure 3. The receiving and transmitting transducers were placed one inch apart on the composite plate along the fiber direction. Both transducers have a resonance frequency of 5 MHz. Measurements were taken with the transmitting transducer angled at 0°, 11.25°, 22.5°, 33.75°, and 45° to the surface normal. The excitation pulse into the composite part was provided by a MATEC TB-1000 pulser/receiver board. It imparted a 1 MHz, 2.0 μsec , high voltage signal every 6.0 msec into the transmitting transducer. The signal was then sent to a PAC IAD-90 ADC that displayed the received signal. A comparison of the response of the plates when the transmitting transducer is at 11.25° is shown in Figure 4. Samples of these signals for a poorly bonded plate at different angles are shown in Figure 5. The differences in the signal between poorly bonded and more

well-bonded plates are probably caused by partial reflection at the bond resulting in frequency dependent mode propagation.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

This preliminary investigation has indicated that there are noticeable differences in the signal output from a well-bonded versus a poorly bonded plate. Future research includes attempting this procedure in an air coupled setting and quantifying the difference between signals. Then the system will be automated so that composite parts may be scanned quickly. Also alternative strength measuring tests will be investigated.

REFERENCES

1. Henneke, Edmund G., II, Reflection-refraction of a stress wave at a plate boundary between anisotropic media. *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **51**, 210-217.
2. Green, W.A. and Dragan Milosavljevic, Extensional waves in strongly anisotropic elastic plates. *Int. J. Solids Structures* **21**, 343-353.
3. Kline, R.A., M.M. Doroudian, and C.P. Hsiao, Plate Wave Propagation in transversely isotropic materials. *J. Comp. Materials* **23**, 505-533.
4. Hosten, B., M. Deschamps, and B.R. Tittmann, Inhomogeneous wave generation and propagation in lossy anisotropic solids. Application to the characterization of viscoelastic composite materials. *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **82**, 1763-1770.
5. Rokhlin, S. I. and W. Wang, Critical angle measurement of elastic constants in composite material. *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **86**, 1876-1882.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS The authors wish to acknowledge the support of NSF (DDM-9309926), ICI Fiberite, Hercules Aerospace Company, and Boeing Commercial Aircraft.

a. Photomicrograph of a well-bonded part.
Sample number 1.

b. Photomicrograph of a poorly bonded part. Sample number 3.

Figure 1. Photomicrographs. Magnification is approximately 35X.

Figure 2. Schematic diagram of the ultrasonic testing system. The angled transducer is used to transmit the excitation pulse.

Figure 3. Comparison of flatwise tensile strength testing results. A completely well-bonded specimen has not broken at any of these loads.

Figure 4. Signal response for various samples. The two 5 MHz transducers are an inch apart. The input pulse is a 1 MHz, 6 μ sec, high voltage tone burst. The transmitting transducer is at an angle of 11.25 deg. Sample 1 was made according to the manufacturer's specifications. The other samples were not.

Figure 4 (con't). Signal response for various samples. The two 5 MHz transducers are an inch apart. The input pulse is a 1MHz, 6 μ sec, high voltage tone burst. The transmitting transducer is at an angle of 11.25 deg. Sample 1 was made according to the manufacturer's specifications. The other samples were not.

Figure 5. Signal response for sample number 3. The two 5 MHz transducers are an inch apart. The input pulse is a 1MHz, 6 μ sec, high voltage tone burst.

Figure 5 (con't). Signal response for sample number 3. The two 5 MHz transducers are an inch apart. The input pulse is a 1MHz, 6 μ sec, high voltage tone burst.